

Scientific impact and researchers' happiness

Joaquín M. Azagra-Caro^{1,*}, Ana Tur-Porcar²

¹ *INGENIO (CSIC-UPV), Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera s/n, E-46022 Valencia, Spain*

² *Universitat de València, Avda. Blasco Ibáñez, 10, E-46010 Valencia, Spain*

Abstract

Scientific impact is key to progress and rewarding for researchers. However, the culture of scientific impact puts researchers under competitive pressure, especially when career advances are based on quantitative indicators of scientific impact. The objective of this study is to analyse the effect of scientific impact on the happiness of researchers. Our findings, based on one of the largest two-wave surveys of researchers so far (over 2,200 Spanish researchers), reveal a negative effect of scientific impact on researchers' happiness. This effect is mitigated by the enhancement of work/personal life, indicating the role of achieving a harmonious balance between professional success and personal life. Our study uncovers the positive moderating influences of prosocial motivation and creativity on the relationship between scientific impact and work/personal life enhancement. These findings underscore the importance of cultivating an environment that nurtures scientific impact based on the motivation to contribute to society and creative processes.

1. Introduction

The pursuit of scientific impact serves as a driver of technological advancement and innovation. Researchers, motivated by discovery and excellence, channel their energies into generating contributions that push the frontiers of knowledge. Yet, a fundamental question emerges: does the quest for impact contribute to or detract from the happiness of researchers at the forefront of science?

Happiness is “the experience of joy, contentment, or positive well-being, combined with a sense that one’s life is good, meaningful, and worthwhile” (Lyubomirsky, 2008). Scientific impact, marked by accolades, citations, and groundbreaking contributions, is traditionally perceived as a source of pride and fulfilment. Scholars like Merton (1957) and Deci & Ryan (2000) argue that recognition for one’s work fosters intrinsic motivation, creating a sense of purpose rooted in the joy of discovery. However, the pursuit of impact, characterised by heightened competition and expectations, may come at the cost of researchers’ happiness. Unfortunately, the literature on the antecedents and consequences of scientific impact has not addressed its relationships with researchers’ happiness.

In this exploration, we posit that the effect of scientific impact on researchers’ happiness is mediated by the enhancement of work/personal life balance. The lens of Hayman (2005) offers a nuanced understanding of this balance, encompassing elements such as deriving energy from personal life for professional endeavours and experiencing an improved mood at work due to personal life satisfaction.

Moreover, we delve into the role of individual motivations as crucial moderators. Prosocial motivation, rooted in the desire to contribute to others’ well-being (Grant, 2008), and creativity,

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +34963877007; fax: +34963877991. E-mail address: jazagra@ingenio.upv.es

as a catalyst for innovative thinking (Jaussi et al., 2007), are examined as potential influencers that either amplify or mitigate the impact of scientific success on overall happiness.

As we navigate this terrain, the paper unfolds with a synthesis of theoretical underpinnings and empirical findings. The objective is to analyse if prosocial motivation and creativity improve the effect of scientific impact on researchers' happiness through the achievement of work/personal life enhancement.

2. Data and methods

The study population consists of Spanish researchers, defined as authors of scientific publications, affiliated to a Spanish organisation, and is taken from the corresponding authors on publications in the WoS from 2013 to 2016.

We gathered some 65,000 valid e-mails. To launch the survey, we obtained ethical certificates from our two mother organisations, CSIC and the Polytechnic University of Valencia. We conducted two waves, to lag the independent and moderating variables. This is the main strength of this study, that reduces common method bias and endogeneity.

For the first wave, we ran a first pilot test in July 2017, a second pilot in April 2018, and the definitive survey was administered between July and November 2018. We received over 7,300 responses; that is, a response rate of 11% and a sample size with a 95% confidence level and a 1% margin of error, which is representative of the population.

For the second wave, we ran a first pilot test in January 2022, a second pilot in March 2022, and the definitive survey was administered between May and July 2022. We received almost 2,500 responses; that is, a response rate of 34% and a sample size with a 95% confidence level and a 1% margin of error, which is representative of the population.

The dependent variable is *happiness*, gathered in 2022. The survey included the four-item Subjective Happiness Scale (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999), validated in Spanish (Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2014). All items were scored in a range between 1 and 7. Reliability was high with Cronbach's alpha of .85.

The independent variable is past *scientific impact*. We measured it as Field Normalised Citation Score (FNCS). In a first step, for each paper, we divided the number of forward citations (a two-year window: publication year and the following two years) by the average number of forward citations received by all Spanish papers in that thematic category and that year. In a second step, we grouped all the papers for every corresponding author and averaged the FNCS. Finally, because the distribution was unbalanced, we transformed it into quartiles, so the final variable ranged between 1 and 4.

The mediating variable is *work/personal life enhancement balance*, which ranged from 1 to 7. The survey contained this four-item subscale a larger Work Life Balance Scale (Hayman, 2005, see in Appendix Table A3). Reliability was high with Cronbach's alpha of .82.

The first moderating variable is *prosocial motivation*, gathered in 2018. We incorporated the eight-item Intrinsic and Prosocial Motivation Scale (Grant, 2008), and obtained a solution with two factors: intrinsic motivation (Cronbach's alpha of .82) and prosocial motivation (Cronbach's alpha of .82). We include intrinsic motivation as a control variable and prosocial motivation as a moderating variable.

The second moderating variable is *creative personal identity*, gathered in 2018. Its measure comes from the four-item Creative Personality Identity Scale (Jaussi et al., 2007, Cronbach's alpha of .82).

We controlled for a wide range of institutional (science field, multidisciplinary, country and region of residence), sociodemographic (sex, age, nationality, language, education, civil status, number of children, employment situation) and organisational (number of organisations,

ownership regime, directive positions) variables. Very important, we control for psychological variables of special interest: to reduce social desirability bias, we include self-deceptive enhancement and impression management, generated through the 16-item Balanced Inventory of Desirable Responding Short Form (Hart et al., 2015), based on Spanish translations (Mikulic et al., 2017; de la Rubia et al., 2012); to not overestimate the effect of prosocial motivation, we include intrinsic motivation, also as in Grant (2008).

We removed collectives whose happiness would likely differ too much from the average researcher, e.g. retired researchers – because some of them would likely want to gain distance from the profession and be worried with health problems – and unemployed researchers – worried about their professional instability. This way we had a relatively more homogeneous population. The final sample also excluded outliers of some of the control variables, e.g., abnormally high age or large number of children. Hence, the number of observations for the estimations is 2,217.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics.

{TABLE 1}

3. Results

As the first two columns of Fig. 3 shows, employed researchers with over average happiness score lower in scientific impact. The difference is even higher among tenured academic researchers – a more homogeneous group that we will use later for a robustness check.

{FIGURE 1}

Table 2 presents the results for estimating researchers' happiness. To reduce collinearity, we present stepwise models in which insignificant variables are progressively dropped.

{TABLE 2}

Column 1 includes a regression without the mediating variable, work/life personal enhancement. Scientific impact conflicts with happiness.

Testing the mediation of science-art balance requires two steps (Mihalache et al., 2014; Baron and Kenny, 1986). First, we need to estimate work/life personal enhancement as a function of scientific impact. That the estimated effect is significant is a precondition for mediation. Column 2 shows that this is the case: scientific impact has a negative, significant effect on work/life personal enhancement.

Hence, we can proceed to add work/life personal enhancement as an independent variable in Column 3, again with happiness as dependent variable. Work/life personal enhancement enters with a positive and significant coefficient, meaning that it fosters happiness. Its inclusion also removes the significance of scientific impact on happiness.

We interact scientific impact with prosocial motivation and creativity in Column 4 to estimate their moderating effects on work/life personal enhancement. The effect of this interaction is positively significant in the case of prosocial motivation, but not significant in the case of creativity.

Among the effects of control variables on happiness, there is institutional heterogeneity regarding scientific fields and regions of residence: belonging to the field of Medicine and living in Barcelona are beneficial conditions for happiness. Being a woman, being married and having several children are also favourable for happiness. Self-deceptive enhancement deters

happiness – which suggests the importance of controlling for social desirability bias –, whereas intrinsic motivation and creativity facilitate it. Other control variables are not influential.

4. Conclusions

This paper contributes to the literature on scientific impact, and more specifically to the consequences of scientific impact. The theoretical contribution is that scientific impact has a negative effect on researchers' happiness due to a discordance between professional success and personal life. The empirical contribution is an estimation of this negative effect based on the largest two-wave survey to researchers so far, which accounts for endogeneity, common method and desirability biases.

First, the study reveals nuanced relationships between scientific impact and researchers' happiness. While achieving high scientific impact may instil a sense of accomplishment, pride, and purpose, it also introduces pressures and stressors that can negatively affect overall happiness.

Second, work/personal life enhancement emerges as a critical mediator, playing a crucial role in balancing the demands of high scientific impact. A harmonious and enriched personal life acts as a safeguard, mitigating potential negative effects and contributing to researchers' overall happiness.

Third, prosocial motivation proves to be a positive moderator, suggesting that researchers driven by a desire to contribute to others' well-being experience an amplified positive effect on both work and personal life. This underscores the importance of fostering a prosocial work environment, with shared prosocial goals among colleagues.

Fourth, creativity also plays a crucial role, positively moderating the relationship between scientific impact and work/personal life enhancement, particularly among tenured academic researchers. The ability to approach work with creativity not only enhances job satisfaction but extends its positive effects to personal life.

Implications for academic institutions include fostering prosocial environments, encouraging prosocial motivation, and recognizing the value of creativity in research. Additionally, recognizing the importance of work/personal life balance is crucial for promoting the well-being of researchers.

Policy implications highlight the need for evaluating and rewarding scientific impact while considering its potential impact on researchers' happiness. Balancing the pursuit of impact with measures supporting overall well-being is crucial for a sustainable and fulfilling academic environment.

Acknowledgements

This study is part of the R&D Project AICO\2021\21, funded by the Valencian Government. The authors are indebted to Carlos Benito-Amat for the provision of scientometrics data.

References

- de la Rubia, J. M., Cadena, C. H. G., & Casas, C. J. A. (2012). Traducción y validación del Inventario Balanceado de Deseabilidad Social al Responder en una muestra probabilística de estudiantes universitarios mexicanos. *Revista de Psicología GEPU*, 3(2), 54-72.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.

- Extremera, N., & Fernández-Berrocal, P. (2014). The Subjective Happiness Scale: Translation and preliminary psychometric evaluation of a Spanish version. *Social Indicators Research*, 119(1), 473-481.
- Grant, A. M. (2008). Does intrinsic motivation fuel the prosocial fire? Motivational synergy in predicting persistence, performance, and productivity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 93(1), 48.
- Hart, C. M., Ritchie, T. D., Hepper, E. G., & Gebauer, J. E. (2015). The balanced inventory of desirable responding short form (BIDR-16). *Sage Open*, 5(4), 2158244015621113.
- Hayman, J. (2005). Psychometric assessment of an instrument designed to measure work life balance. *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, 13(1), 85-91.
- Jaussi, K. S., Randel, A. E., & Dionne, S. D. (2007). I am, I think I can, and I do: The role of personal identity, self-efficacy, and cross-application of experiences in creativity at work. *Creativity Research Journal*, 19(2-3), 247-258.
- Lyubomirsky, S. (2008). *The how of happiness: A scientific approach to getting the life you want*. Penguin.
- Lyubomirsky, S., & Lepper, H. S. (1999). A measure of subjective happiness: Preliminary reliability and construct validation. *Social Indicators Research*, 46(2), 137-155.
- Merton, R. K. (1957). Priorities in scientific discovery: A chapter in the sociology of science. *American Sociological Review*, 22(6), 635-659.
- Mikulic, I. M., Crespi, M., & Caballero, R. (2016). Estudio psicométrico del Inventario Balanceado de Respuesta Deseable. *Anuario de Psicología*, 46(2), 58-66.

Tables and figures

Table 1. Spanish employed researchers (n=2,217): Descriptive statistics of variables

Role	Level	Variable name	Description/Explanation	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Dependent variable	Psychological	Happiness	Degree to which researchers experience happiness in their lives	-0.01	0.90	-3.75	1.59
Independent variable	Individual	Scientific impact (H1)	Average Field Normalized Citation Score of the researcher's publications, grouped in 4 quartiles	2.49	1.11	1.00	4.00
Mediating variable	Psychological	Work/personal life enhancement (H2)	Degree to which researchers positively combine their work and personal facets	-0.03	0.89	-2.46	2.76
Moderating variables	Psychological	Prosocial motivation (H3)	Degree to which researchers are motivated to benefit others	5.12	1.00	1.00	7.00
		Creative personal identity (H4)	Degree to which researchers feel creative	4.55	0.42	3.00	6.00
Control variables	Institutional	Science field	Medicine	0.24	0.40	0.00	1.00
			Life Sciences	0.16	0.33	0.00	1.00
			Other Natural Sciences	0.25	0.39	0.00	1.00
			Engineering	0.14	0.31	0.00	1.00
		Social Sciences and Humanities	0.21	0.38	0.00	1.00	
		Multidisciplinarity	Number of science fields	0.34	0.48	0.00	1.00
		Region of residence	Madrid	0.24	0.43	0.00	1.00
	Barcelona		0.09	0.28	0.00	1.00	
	Valencia ('other Spanish regions' is the initial benchmark)		0.10	0.30	0.00	1.00	
	Sociodemographic	Foreign residence	Non-Spanish residence	0.04	0.20	0.00	1.00
			Woman researcher	Sex of the researcher	0.44	0.50	0.00
		Age	Number of years	47.74	9.29	18.00	79.00
		Foreign nationality	'Spanish only' is the benchmark	0.06	0.23	0.00	1.00
		Non-Spanish first language	'Spanish only' is the benchmark	0.21	0.41	0.00	1.00
		PhD	PhD title	0.91	0.29	0.00	1.00
		Married or domestic partner	'Couple or single' is the benchmark	0.67	0.47	0.00	1.00
	Psychological	Number of underage children	Father/motherhood	0.82	1.00	0.00	5.00
Working for others			Employee, salaried worker, not self-employed	0.98	0.14	0.00	1.00
Self-deceptive enhancement			Degree to which researchers believe something to be true when it is not, even if they are not aware of portraying themselves positively nor consciously trying to	4.13	0.47	2.00	6.13
Impression management		Degree to which researchers are intentionally seeking to keep up with social or group norms to avoid negative evaluation or judgment	3.93	0.55	1.00	5.88	
Intrinsic motivation		Degree to which researchers are motivated based on interest in and enjoyment of the work itself	5.92	0.85	1.00	7.00	

Fig. 1. Scientific impact by degree of happiness, under and over average (employed researchers, n=2,217; tenured academic researchers, n=1,201). Mean-comparison t tests indicate 5%-significant differences of scientific impact between groups.

Table 2. Stepwise linear regression of happiness and work/personal life enhancement: employed researchers.

	1 Happiness	2 Work/personal life enhancement	3 Happiness	4 Work/personal life enhancement
Medicine	0.12*** (0.05)		0.10*** (0.04)	
Social Sciences	0.09* (0.05)	0.09* (0.05)		
Madrid		-0.11** (0.04)		-0.11*** (0.04)
Barcelona	0.13** (0.06)		0.09* (0.06)	
Woman researcher	0.07** (0.04)		0.07** (0.03)	
Age		0.01*** (0.00)		0.01*** (0.00)
Non-Spanish 1 st language		-0.10** (0.04)		-0.10** (0.04)
Married/domestic partner	0.20*** (0.04)		0.16*** (0.04)	
N. of children underage	0.04** (0.02)	0.04** (0.02)	0.03* (0.02)	0.04** (0.02)
Working for others			-0.19* (0.11)	
Self-deceptive enhancement	-0.20*** (0.04)		-0.18*** (0.04)	
Impression management			-0.05* (0.03)	
Intrinsic motivation	0.22*** (0.03)	0.22*** (0.02)	0.11*** (0.02)	0.22*** (0.02)
Extrinsic motivation	0.05** (0.02)	0.04* (0.02)		0.04* (0.02)
Prosocial motivation		0.12*** (0.02)		0.13*** (0.02)
Creative personal identity	0.18*** (0.05)		0.15*** (0.04)	
Scientific impact (H1)	-0.03** (0.02)	-0.03** (0.02)		-0.04** (0.02)
Work/personal life enhancement (H2)			0.40*** (0.02)	
Scientific impact * Prosocial motivation (H3)				0.05*** (0.02)
Constant	0.59*** (0.17)	-0.43*** (0.10)	0.94*** (0.21)	-0.40*** (0.10)
N	2239	2217	2217	2217
F	18	23	58	24
p	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
R ²	0.10	0.11	0.24	0.11

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01. Robust standard errors in parenthesis. No multicollinearity according to VIF.

Happiness and work/personal life enhancement measured in 2022. Other psychological and control variables measured in 2018. Scientific impact of 2013-2016 publications with a two-year window.

Dropped variables: Life Sciences, Other Natural Sciences, Engineering, Multidisciplinarity, Valencia, Other region, Foreign residence, Foreign nationality, PhD, Scientific impact squared, Scientific impact * Creative personal identity (H4)